

DMS Accelerator Needs Analysis

The aim of this set of questions is to elaborate upon the responses of your application form. As you are aware, DMS accelerator offers a wide range of services. To fine tune these services, it is convenient to identify what are the most important needs of your company. Please answer the following question, focusing on the needs of your startup for the next six months.

* Required

1. Company Name *

Service categories

2. Service categories: Please rank the above categories, from the most important (1) to the least important (5). *

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
Promoting your company	<input type="radio"/>				
Fundraising	<input type="radio"/>				
Upskilling your workforce	<input type="radio"/>				
Data compliance management	<input type="radio"/>				
IP management	<input type="radio"/>				
Entrepreneurial skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Explore international markets	<input type="radio"/>				

Acceleration services

3. PROMOTING YOUR COMPANY: From 1 (not at all) to 5 (absolutely), how well do you think the following services would suit the needs of your company? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
Attendance to conferences and events, where DMS provides a ticket and a booth	<input type="radio"/>				
Audiovisual production of marketing material	<input type="radio"/>				
Promotion in our social media channels	<input type="radio"/>				
Digital marketing training via webinars	<input type="radio"/>				

4. Please briefly explain the reason for your choices

5. Can you think of another related service that would be beneficial for accelerating your company?

6. FUNDRAISING: From 1 (not at all) to 5 (absolutely), how well do you think the following services would suit the needs of your company? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
Introduction and matchmaking with investors at the appropriate round of investment	<input type="radio"/>				
Pitch deck design training via webinars	<input type="radio"/>				
Pitching to investors training via webinars	<input type="radio"/>				

7. Please briefly explain the reason for your choices

8. Can you think of another related service that would be beneficial for accelerating your company?

9. ENTREPRENEURIAL TRAININGS: From 1 (not at all) to 5 (absolutely), how well do you think the following services would suit the needs of your company? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
How to develop Buisness plan	<input type="radio"/>				
How to develop products and plans	<input type="radio"/>				
How to improve your sales process	<input type="radio"/>				

10. Please briefly explain the reason for your choices

11. Can you think of another related service that would be beneficial for accelerating your company?

12. Can you think of another related service that would be beneficial for accelerating your company?

13. MANAGING YOUR DATA FOR COMPLIANCE: From 1 (not at all) to 5 (absolutely), how well do you think the following services would suit the needs of your company? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
GDPR training via an online course	<input type="radio"/>				
GDPR training via webinars	<input type="radio"/>				
Data standardisation and legal compliance training via webinars	<input type="radio"/>				
Data standardisation and legal compliance via 1-1 tutoring	<input type="radio"/>				

14. Please briefly explain the reason for your choices

15. Can you think of another related service that would be beneficial for accelerating your company?

16. MANAGING YOUR INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY: From 1 (not at all) to 5 (absolutely), how well do you think the following services would suit the needs of your company?

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
IP management via webinars	<input type="radio"/>				
IP management via 1-1 mentoring	<input type="radio"/>				

17. Please briefly explain the reason for your choices

18. Can you think of another related service that would be beneficial for accelerating your company?

19. Are you interested in having a coach during the 6 months of the programme?
Please, note that this will require time to meet with coaches at least twice a month (ca.1h) *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

20. Are you ready to be the next DMS Success Story? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

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